

DIFFERENCES IN THE USE OF LANGUAGE BY UZBEK MEN AND WOMEN IN SHAPING EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION PROCESS IN THE SOCIAL ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the differences in the use of language by Uzbek men and women in the formation of an effective communication process in the social environment. In linguistics, the theoretical understanding of the interaction and connection of gender characteristics in the process of communication is highlighted.

Introduction.

Purposeful formation of these processes in the science of psychology, different from directly formed social knowledge or communicative literacy, which is formed in the process of increasing personal experience, social skills and skills during a person's life, is one of the urgent issues of today. The social development of a person is his normal development, socialization, the process of his formation as a person, his relationship with society cannot be realized without communication. Communication is considered a unique social need of a person. Perfect people's manners of behavior, way of thinking, readability of getting into a relationship, ability to get out of a situation are also imitated by other people and live according to it in their life experience. Raising young people so that they are not only physically strong, but also spiritually rich, meet the demands of the new era, and think freely in the process of communication is one of the urgent problems of today. Regarding the role of communication in personality development, psychologists A.A.Lyublinskaya, D.B.Elkonin emphasize the formation of communication in children through play activities. P.Y. Galperin, N.F. Dobro'nin, N.F. Talizina conducted their research on the formation of character and voluntary qualities of a person through communication.

"Communication is a multifaceted process of the development of bonds between people arising from the needs of joint activities." Communication (relationship) involves the exchange of information between the participants. This takes into account the communicative aspect of the relationship. People turn to language first when entering into a relationship.

The study of speech and gender is an interdisciplinary work of scholars in the fields of linguistics, anthropology, speech communication, social psychology, education, literature, and other disciplines. Many researchers have been primarily concerned with documenting gendered patterns of language use, but the field has also encompassed many where the social

and political aspects of gender relations can be seen in language learning. The tension between these two perspectives emerged in early research and continues today, as evidenced by exchanges between, for example, Preisler (1998) and Cameron (1999). Regardless of the perspective from which the research originates, the study of gender and discourse not only provides descriptive information on male/female discourse, but also how language functions as a symbolic resource to create and manage personal, social, and cultural meanings. shows. and identities. As our understanding of the relationship between language and gender has deepened, researchers have come to many similar, often unacknowledged, or widely recognized conclusions. This article reflects on and analyzes the most widely accepted principles and most debated issues that have emerged.

The development of scientific thinking causes the change of theoretical views in any field of science, the creation of new methods of research, and the achievement of completely different practical results based on the reliance on new theoretical ideas in the application of these methods. Such changes in the scientific process occur as a result of stage analysis, the formation and systematic introduction of theoretical conclusions in the continuous research process. Language is always related to human life and social activities. One of the main tasks of today's linguistics is to take into account the social system in which a person lives in order to know the social function of a linguistic sign and how to use it.

Today's new paradigm, gender linguistics, has brought with it a number of objects of study. Gender-linguistic analysis of the work of art reveals the inherent complexity of the gender characteristics of the images in it. In order to determine the general linguistic essence of genderology, first of all, it is necessary to determine its relationship with other related, bordering fields, the aspects that ensure its organic connection, as well as the characteristics of signs that reflect individual characteristics. In the early gender-linguistic studies, more attention was paid to the gender characteristics of the use of language tools, and the study of the place of gender parameters in linguistics was not given serious importance. Nowadays, interest in conducting gender studies in linguistics is growing, and ideas about the role of language in society have also changed radically. The process of realization of gender phenomena in speech communication and linguistic activity is shared with linguistic phenomena that have a different content and essence. It is known that the speaker uses a linguistic system that is the same for everyone, regardless of gender or class. However, it is important to note that each individual's speech or language ability and level of opportunity will be different. Gender-linguistic research of artistic text, language units in general is one of the important tasks of today's linguistics. The issue of researching the relationship between language and gender parameters has been widely and comprehensively studied in Western and Russian linguistics, a number of studies have been conducted and are still ongoing. This problem was also raised in Uzbek linguistics. Many specialists are attracting attention, including: M. Kurbanova, S. Boymirzaeva, N. Bekmukhamedova and B. Yoldoshev. International conferences have been regularly held in this field. Following the research, Muhabbat Kurbanova emphasizes that special attention is being paid to two aspects in this field:

1. Women and men express their thoughts in a specific way when describing a certain reality or its fragment or in other situations (*gender characteristic of speech*);

2. A lot of attention is paid and analyzed to the existence of linguistic tools that express the concept of femininity and masculinity in a specific language system (*distinguishing men and women from each other in the language system, defining language units that serve to differentiate*).

The study of the speech behavior of women and men has become prominent in Russian and European linguistics. In world linguistics, the gender problem is studied in various aspects. Gender is the difference between men and women according to the general meaning. The speech behavior of both sexes in the world linguistics, the German scientist Jules Oates in his work "woman, man and language" also reveals the mutually different aspects of the speech of women and men. It assumes a gender perspective by comparing the negative and positive connotations of more women and men. It assumes a gender perspective by comparing the negative and positive connotations of more women and men. The men talk about politics, world news, sports and cars. Also, their speech shows more calmness, restraint, and management in their mentality. In women's speech, there are more topics such as lamentation, longing, household, family. Women express their joy sometimes through high level emotions and various non-verbal events (*screaming, clapping, etc.*). But anger, which is a negative personality trait, is stronger in men than in women.

While women express their anger by remaining silent and silent, men often hide their anger by yelling, cursing and other non-verbal phenomena. A specific aspect of women's and men's speech. When comparing swearing and profanity by age, swearing in women's speech is more common among women over 40 years old.

Of course, it is relative to express a strong opinion that men's speech is suitable for calmness and restraint, and for women's speech, lamentation and regret are appropriate. Also, when distinguishing such cases, as we mentioned above, it is necessary to take into account the social status of the person. For example, there is a difference between the speech of an educated, intelligent teacher and the speech of an ordinary housewife. Considering the goal of research to define the subject of linguistic activity as a person with a socio-biological status, it can be said that it is an integral part of sociolinguistics. According to sociologists, gender can be used in social terms to refer to the social division of society into men and women. Social factors such as class, age, race, and origin shape the expression and experience of particular gender content. From the point of view of terminology, the concept of gender was formed during the theoretical development of feminism, directly in the process of gender studies.

Research is one of the youngest and most promising scientific directions in the world. It covers law, family relations, health, literature, culture, etc. Gender linguistics studies the problems related to the role of a person belonging to a gender in social processes or other aspects of life. The gender approach is not based on biological or physical differences between men and women, but on the cultural and social values defined by the dominant society. In the gender analysis of social relations, gender discrepancy is determined. The meaning of the concept of "gender" is first of all organized with the help of social gender, social practice embodied in the social modeling or organization of gender.

Researching the use of gender parameters in linguistics has also proven to be important in the study of feminine or masculine constructivist principles of linguistics. The main goal of

gender research in linguistics is to determine the types and causes of the phenomenon of "linguistic asymmetry" in the form of differences in written or spoken texts, characteristic of women's and men's speech, as well as in the style of both sexes. From spoken speech to written texts, there are different types of idiosyncrasies. When examining the structure of the texts, the phonetic, lexical-phraseological, stylistic and other types of differences between women's and men's speech are clearly visible. It is necessary to identify the individual characteristics of women's or men's speech and their linguistic activity, to carry out effective analysis and research in this regard. As experts rightly point out, when any type of text is studied from the perspective of genderology, it is possible to determine the social and ethnocultural reasons for the choice of language units made by the author. Gender features of speech that are characteristic only of women in Uzbek language can be characteristic of representatives of both sexes in some foreign languages. It will be up to the researchers studying the gender characteristics of the Uzbek language to prove this point. There is no doubt that effective use of comparative analysis methods in the study of gender characteristics in linguistics will give the expected results. Conclusion In conclusion, it can be said that the theory of gender in Uzbek linguistics is an important part of the general study of the language. To better understand how language works in general, it is important to understand how gender works in Uzbek linguistics. The theories discussed in this article serve as a useful basis for understanding gender in Uzbek linguistics.

Conclusion.

Linguistics research is increasingly turning to gender and discourse studies (*although variation studies such as Eckert 1989, 1998 suggest a promising symbiotic relationship between quantitative and qualitative methods*). The drive to learn language within a specific activity reflects the importance of language strategies and culturally defined meanings of gender. It recognizes the agency of individuals in the creation of gender identities, including the potential to resist and subvert sociocultural norms for language behavior. But she also acknowledges the socio-cultural constraints that women and men exercise on their language choices, and the effects of these constraints on whether they adhere to or reject them. In a sense, the field of gender and discourse has come full circle and returned to a Goffman-influenced constructivist framework, as seen in the innovative work of Brown, Goodwin, Lakoff, and Goffman himself.

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